

SCRIPT CREACIÓN TABLAS DE IMAGEN MEDICAL IMAGE EXTENSION


```
CREATE TABLE image_occurrence(  
    image_occurrence_id bigint NOT NULL  
CONSTRAINT imag_occur_pk PRIMARY KEY,  
    person_id bigint NOT NULL,  
    procedure_occurrence_id bigint NOT NULL,  
    visit_occurrence_id bigint NULL,  
    anatomic_site_concept_id integer NULL,  
    wadors_uri varchar(max) NULL,  
    local_path varchar(max) NOT NULL,  
    image_occurrence_date date NOT NULL,  
    image_study_uid varchar(250) NOT NULL,  
    image_series_uid varchar(250) NOT NULL,  
    modality_concept_id integer NOT NULL  
)
```

```
CREATE TABLE image_feature (  
    image_feature_id bigint NOT NULL  
CONSTRAINT rad_img_pk PRIMARY KEY,  
    person_id bigint NOT NULL,  
    image_occurrence_id bigint NOT NULL,  
    table_concept_id integer NOT NULL,  
    table_row_id integer NOT NULL,  
    image_feature_concept_id integer NOT NULL,  
    image_feature_type_concept_id integer NOT NULL,  
    image_finding_concept_id integer NULL,  
    image_finding_id integer NULL,  
    anatomic_site_concept_id integer NULL,  
    alg_system varchar(max) NULL,  
    alg_datetime timestamp NULL  
)
```

--A CONTINUACIÓN SE MUESTRAN LAS TABLAS Y SECUENCIAS AÑADIDAS POR
--VERATECH PARA LA CARGA DE LOS DATOS A OMOP.

```
CREATE TABLE correspondencia_pacientes (  
    source_id  VARCHAR    NOT NULL,  
    OMOP_id    INT      NOT NULL  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE correspondencia_visitas (  
    source_id  VARCHAR    NOT NULL,  
    OMOP_id    INT      NOT NULL  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE correspondencia_image_occurrence (  
    source_id  VARCHAR    NOT NULL,  
    OMOP_id    INT      NOT NULL  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE correspondencia_image_feature (  
    source_id  VARCHAR    NOT NULL,  
    OMOP_id    INT      NOT NULL  
);
```

-- SECUENCIAS:

```
CREATE SEQUENCE person_id  
START WITH 1  
INCREMENT BY 1  
MINVALUE 0  
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE visist_occurrence_id  
START WITH 1  
INCREMENT BY 1  
MINVALUE 0  
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE image_occurrence_id  
START WITH 1  
INCREMENT BY 1  
MINVALUE 0  
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE image_feature_id  
START WITH 1  
INCREMENT BY 1  
MINVALUE 0  
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE condition_occurrence_id
START WITH 1
INCREMENT BY 1
MINVALUE 0
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE measurement_id
START WITH 1
INCREMENT BY 1
MINVALUE 0
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE observation_id
START WITH 1
INCREMENT BY 1
MINVALUE 0
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```

```
CREATE SEQUENCE procedure_id
START WITH 1
INCREMENT BY 1
MINVALUE 0
MAXVALUE 999999999999;
```